

Goldbach's Prime Triangle

A recreational math journey with an introduction to equidistant primes

by Jörg Winkelmann¹

Abstract

This article explores new ways of visualizing Goldbach's conjecture based on certain underlying properties, notably prime numbers that are equidistant from a given integer n . These so-called *equidistant primes* play a major role in providing a different context and new perspective on the famous conjecture. The presented findings include two distinct methods for generating a graphical representation of the conjecture, combining the sequences of equidistant primes and those of all prime numbers. This specific representation reveals interesting symmetrical properties and is referred to as *Goldbach's Prime Triangle* throughout this paper.

Keywords

Goldbach — Primes — Number Theory

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Introduction

Goldbach's conjecture has fascinated scores of mathematicians and math-enthusiasts across the globe ever since its basic idea was first mentioned in a letter by Christian Goldbach to Leonhard Euler in June 1742[1]. The modern version of Goldbach's conjecture has an intriguingly simple premise:

Every even integer n greater than two is the sum of two primes.

Despite the simplicity of this premise, no method has been found to date that could prove or disprove the conjecture. Number theorists generally view Goldbach's conjecture as a delicate problem. One can say delicate because there are no indications or obvious ways as to how one could go about in order to prove the conjecture true or false.

Computationally, it has been proven to be true for all integers less than $4 \cdot 10^{18}$ [2]. And it is assumed, that it will hold up to infinity, which was also Euler's response to Goldbach while admitting that "he would not be able to demonstrate it". Past research into the subject provided some basic definitions: Two primes that sum to an even integer are known as a Goldbach Partition. The number of different partitions that result in a given integer n is expressed through the Goldbach (partition) Function. Overall, the number of possible partitions for each n increases as n gets larger. It would therefore seem obvious that the conjecture is true, a notion that is further supported by various graphical representations like Goldbach's Comet[3] or the Goldbach Weave[4].

1. Factoring in Patterns: Twin Primes

The fact that prime numbers do not appear to be completely random in nature, especially when viewed as a group, has been shown in various ways, such as the Ulam and Sachs

spirals or Euler's prime-generating polynomial $x^2 - x + 41$ [5]. A rather obvious pattern are twin primes, where $n - 1$ and $n + 1$ of an integer n are both prime numbers. Although still unproven, it is assumed that there are infinitely many twin primes, as research by Terence Tao[6], James Maynard[7], Yitang Zhang[8] and others suggests. So what role do or can twin primes play in regard to Goldbach's conjecture? When exploring the symmetry of twin primes, we find that the key property of twin primes, namely that $n - 1$ and $n + 1$ are prime, can be extended further along the numberline. Let d be the distance of a prime number from n . As n increases, it becomes clear that there are many instances in which $n - d$ and $n + d$ are prime. In the following example we see that, for an integer $n = 12$, there are three such pairs:

Figure 1. Primes equidistant from $n = 12$

All the highlighted integers in Fig. 1 are equidistant from n and therefore share one of the main characteristics of true twin primes. They behave like mirrored prime numbers with regard to their position related to n . Since the term mirror prime is already attributed to a different class of numbers, one could refer to such twin prime analogs as symmetry primes or better: equidistant primes.

Definition: *Equidistant prime numbers are pairs of primes (p_1, p_2) that share the same distance (d) from an integer n , such that $n - d$ and $n + d$ are both prime. Equidistant primes are also Goldbach partitions.*

Figure 2. Goldbach's Prime Triangle

And such primes would not be particularly noteworthy, if the previous example would be a rare occurrence. But quite on the contrary: along the number line, this symmetry of equidistant primes is apparently the rule rather than the exception. By definition, every single prime itself can also be considered to be a set of equidistant primes, since their distance from n is zero ($n - 0$ and $n + 0$, respectively).

In order to visualize the equidistant primes, we create a vertical numberline starting with $n = 3$ and continue down the column as far as we desire, highlighting the prime numbers as we go along. At the top, we have $n = 3$, which is the sole number in our first row. Next, in the second row, we add integers before and after $n = 4$, in order to complete the numberline (3,4,5). We then highlight prime numbers that are equidistant from $n = 4$ (which are 3 and 5). In this fashion, we continue further down, continuously completing the horizontal numberlines and highlighting equidistant primes. Ultimately, this procedure results in the visualization seen in Fig. 2, which we may refer to as Goldbach's Prime Triangle.

When looking at this visualization, it is easy to see how Goldbach's conjecture is encoded in this representation:

$$n - d = p_1 \wedge n + d = p_2 \implies n = \frac{p_1 + p_2}{2} \quad (1)$$

Here, d denotes the distance (from n), where p_1 and p_2 are prime. This is a slightly different way of proceeding compared to similar approaches, but it illustrates the same principle of the conjecture.

2. Multiple Symmetries

Apart from the obvious mirror symmetry along the center axis, Goldbach's Prime Triangle also contains the sequence of all primes greater than 2 along its diagonal axes (\overline{AB} and \overline{AD} , Fig. 3). This illustration then also reveals a translational or rotational symmetry. For instance, the sequence of points on \overline{AC} can be translated to \overline{AB} and \overline{AD} showing the same prime sequence, albeit with half the length. The same is true for the points on \overline{CA} , which can be translated to \overline{CB} and \overline{CD} , respectively. These properties apply to any diamond-shaped section of any size within the prime triangle (as illustrated in Fig. 3 using the outline A,B,C,D), as long as its center is located along the axis \overline{AC} . Accordingly, the prime at point C has corresponding primes at points D and B.

Figure 3. Translational symmetry of the prime triangle

Figure 4. Diagonal bands of composite numbers

3. Primes and Composite Numbers

There is an alternative way of creating the prime triangle: Let us imagine infinitely many points, arranged in a triangle as illustrated in Fig. 4 (a). These points represent the same numbers as the cells in the prime triangle (Fig.2). We can then follow the diagonal axis on the right, starting from the top, and mark each composite number. Then we remove all integers, diagonally from right to left, thus creating diagonal bands as shown in Fig. 4 (b). We now mirror these bands, but this time on the left side (irrespective of the integers represented by each point, it does not matter whether they are prime or composite). Through this procedure, some prime numbers along the bands, created by the composite numbers, are also removed (due to the mirroring on the left side). We further observe, that each band leaves a trail of removed integers for every new row that follows, all the way up to infinity.

We are now left with the sequence of prime numbers on the vertical and diagonal axes. The integers that remain on the horizontal axis (or row/numberline, respectively) are the equidistant primes, which result in the even integers when summed and divided by 2. The bands in Fig. 4 (b), cancel out many integers on their path along the diagonals, but the numberlines/rows constantly grow in size and some equidistant primes always seem to remain.

4. Yet Another Method

In 2012, Cunningham and Ringland published a similar visualization involving a different method[9]. Fig. 5 illustrates how the basic pattern of Goldbach's Prime Triangle also emerges, when highlighting the intersections of diagonals which are represented by primes at their origins. The prime pairs leading to these intersections (marked by the white points) total the corresponding n value of the center column (horizontal line). The outcome is essentially the same as that of Goldbach's Prime Triangle while utilizing a different method and approach.

Figure 5. Goldbach partitions as illustrated by Cunningham and Ringland[9]

5. Observations

When combining the different approaches to create Goldbach's Prime Triangle (Fig. 2 and Fig. 5), there is a strong case to be made for the assumption that Goldbach partitions represent the sequence of all prime numbers *ad infinitum* along the diagonal lines and the center axis in either visualization. As mentioned earlier, this unique pattern can be generated either by highlighting all equidistant primes (Fig. 2) or by marking the intersections of prime pairs, which are located at the origins of the intersecting diagonal lines (Fig. 5). When looking at both of these approaches, we can observe the following:

1. All equidistant primes of Goldbach's Prime Triangle (Fig. 2) have a corresponding point representing the Goldbach partitions of the method by Cunningham and Ringland (Fig. 5).
2. The diagonals of both visualizations, starting at their origins, represent the sequence of all primes (for $n > 2$).
3. Both methods (Fig. 2 and 5) imply that there is a corresponding prime number on the outer diagonals of the triangle for each equidistant prime and for each intersection of prime pairs, respectively.

A break in the pattern of equidistant primes could, for instance, occur when assuming that there are none at all in any given row of Goldbach's Prime Triangle (Fig. 6 and Fig. 7). However, due to the aforementioned observations, as noted in Items 1-3 above, this would cause a disruption of the prime sequences along the diagonals, thus introducing gaps, where there should be prime numbers instead.

Figure 6. Scenario A: no equidistant primes for $n = 8$

Figure 7. Scenario B: no prime pairs for $n = 16$

A complete lack of equidistant primes throughout a row or numberline (as seen in Fig. 6) would thus imply that there

are no Goldbach partitions for a given integer n . Similarly, if we assume that the (outer) diagonal sequences of primes must continue without breaking (as n increases), there must always be partitions for any given n that satisfy Equation 1. In case the aforementioned observations are not too trivial (from a more rigorous standpoint), perhaps they provide a somewhat different and maybe even interesting take on this difficult problem of Goldbach's legacy. A code example for generating a larger pixel-based version of Goldbach's Prime Triangle, using equidistant primes, is available in the reference section[10].

6. Final Thoughts

Having arrived at the findings of this article independently during my research into primes over the years, it still needs to be pointed out that the basic idea of equidistant primes[11] and the general pattern of the prime triangle[4][9] have been mentioned before elsewhere, although involving different approaches, implications and interpretations. Therefore, I thought it might be worth presenting these ideas in a new light, hoping to address some loose ends in the process. Maybe there is some significance to these insights, or maybe not. But at the very least, Goldbach's Prime Triangle provides an additional (and hopefully enjoyable) perspective on the famous conjecture.

Acknowledgments

I would like to thank Professor David Eisenbud (University of California Berkeley), who first reviewed a draft of this paper and encouraged me to bring these findings to the attention of a broader audience.

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